

EFFECT OF WETTABILITY ON MACROVOID FORMATION IN VISCOUS-FLUID IMPREGNATION TO WOVEN FIBER BUNDLES

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ABSTRACT

A series of experiments on impregnation of viscous liquid to single-layer woven glass fiber mat are conducted. We mainly focus on the effect of the wettability between the viscous liquid and fiber bundles. It is found that impregnation velocity changes by varying the wettability. We illustrate how the macrovoids form by tracking the flow front in the fiber bundles under various capillary number. We indicate macrovoid formation is drastically affected by the wettability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) is a composite material combining a resin as a base material and fibers as a reinforcing material. FRP is used extensively in aerospace and other applications because of its advantages of high strength and light weight. As one of the mainstream production methods of this FRP, there are LCM (liquid composite molding) methods such as RTM (resin transfer molding) method and VARTM (vacuum assisted RTM) method. These methods are often used because of their low cost and ability to form complex shapes. In these processes, however, one has to avoid or minimize formation of voids, which are entrapments of residual air created in the material during the manufacturing. This has been an important and critical issue since they degenerate mechanical performances of the product, including bending strength, shear strength between layers, and compressive strength. In order to improve the quality of the product, thus, it is of great importance to optimize the conditions in the manufacturing process and suppress voids.

A number of researches on RTM and VARTM methods have been conducted with unidirectional [1, 2] and woven [3, 4] fibers. It has been found that the formation of voids in VARTM and RTM methods can be correlated with capillary number (Ca), which is a dimensionless number representing the ratio of surface tension and viscous force [5, 6] defined as follows;

$$Ca = \frac{\mu U}{\sigma}, \quad (1)$$

where μ is the dynamic viscosity, σ is the surface tension, and U is the characteristic velocity of the impregnation. Voids can be categorized into two types according to the competition between the viscous flow between the fiber bundles and the capillary wicking in the fiber bundles [7, 8]. When Ca is large, that is, when the viscous force is more dominant than the capillary force for the fluid, voids are created in the fiber bundles by the liquid penetrating and flowing within the fiber bundles. On the contrary, when Ca is small, that is, when the capillary force is more dominant than the viscous force for the fluid, voids are created between the fiber bundles by the liquid flowing along the fiber bundles. The former is generally called as microvoids, and the latter macrovoids. It has been known that, even a small amount of macrovoid leads to a large decrease in mechanical properties [9]. It is rather difficult to specify the optimum Ca for minimizing the macrovoid formation for fiber mat with different structure and geometries, but it is considered that the optimum Ca be around 10^{-3} [1, 10]. Rohatgi et al. [2] proposed modified capillary number (Ca'), taking account of the contact angle θ between liquid and solid as follows;

$$Ca' = \frac{\mu U}{\sigma \cos \theta} \quad (2)$$

Few studies have systematically investigated, however, the effect of this contact angle on the formation of voids.

In this study, we conduct a series of experiments with an interest in the effect of wettability on the impregnation process of woven fiber bundles.

2 EXPERIMENTS

The experimental apparatus used in this research is shown in Figure 1. A single-layer woven glass-fiber mat is used as the reinforcing material. The fiber bundles are placed between smooth acrylic plates and fixed by jigs made of SUS. O-rings are installed between the acrylic plates to prevent inflow and outflow of the gas and the liquid outside the mold. The inlet of the mold and the reservoir containing the test fluid are connected by a suction tube, and the outlet of the mold is also connected to the multipurpose tank by a discharge tube. The tank is connected to a pressure regulator (NVR 200-01, Koganei Corporation, Japan), a pressure gauge (VPC-A4-SA-(-101.3 kPa)-1, VALCOM Co., LTD, Japan), and a vacuum pump (DA-60D, ULVAC, Inc., Japan). The pressure is reduced in the order of the multipurpose tank, the mold, and the test fluid reservoir. Then the test fluid is impregnated into the mold by the pressure difference from the atmospheric pressure. In this study, the gauge pressure in the mold is adjusted by the regulator to a designated value in the range from -0.6 kPa to -5 kPa. These impregnation processes of the viscous liquid is recorded from the bottom of the mold by a CCD camera (C9300-024, HAMAMATSU Photonics K.K., Japan) through the acrylic plate as the bottom wall of the mold. We employ 350 cSt silicone oil (KF-96-350cs, Shin-Etsu Chemical Co., Ltd., Japan) as the test fluid. The kinematic viscosity, density and surface tension of the test fluid under 25°C are of 350 mm²/s, 996.9 kg/m³ and 21.1 mN/m, respectively. As for the test fiber bundles (Figure 2), we use the woven glass fiber mat whose weight density per area is of 550 g/m². The diameter of the fiber of 17 μm. We prepare the mat of 200 mm in the net flow direction (x direction in Fig. 2) and of 100 mm in the vertical direction (y direction in Fig. 2). The fiber bundles parallel to the net flow direction are defined as the warp, and the vertical ones are defined as the weft. Whole experiments are conducted under a constant room temperature at 22 °C.

Figure 1. Experimental apparatus for observing impregnation behavior of viscous fluid into Woven glass-fiber mat.

Figure 2. Picture of woven glass-fiber mat used in this research.

In order to investigate the effect of the wettability on the impregnation, we prepare two kinds of fiber mat; the one is the bare mat, and the other is the coated with a fluorine-based coating agent (RFH-10, RYOKO CHEMICAL CO., LTD, Japan). The former mat has a better wettability against the test fluid. Although the precise contact angle between the fiber and the test liquid is hard to be determined, we evaluate the effect of fluorine-based coating agent on the wettability as shown in Fig. 3. We prepare (a) the bare glass plate and (b) a glass plate with the coating, and put a droplet of the test fluid. The contact angle on (a) the bare glass plate is evaluated as 17° , and that on (b) the coated glass plate as 71° . In the present study, these values are adopted as the contact angles.

Figure 3. Wettability of the test fluid against (a) the bare glass plate and (b) a glass plate coated with fluorine-based coating agent.

3 RESULTS&DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows examples of temporal variation of the averaged impregnation rate under different ΔP for bare fiber mat. This rate is evaluated from the impregnation process of the viscous fluid within the field of view. Characteristic impregnation velocity U_0 is then calculated from these impregnation rate as follows.

$$U_0 = \frac{\Delta I_m}{\Delta t} \cdot \frac{S}{L_y} \quad (3)$$

where ΔI_m is the variation of the average impregnation rate within a period Δt , S is the area of the field of view, and L_y is the length of the field of view parallel to the inlet or vertical to the net flow direction. Here, the averaged impregnation rate is evaluated by analyzing the change of the brightness in the field of view before and after the fluid impregnation. The averaged impregnation rate increases with a nearly constant slope under all pressure difference and finally converges to a constant value. In this study, the slope of the averaged impregnation rate in a region between $0.3 \lesssim I_{avg} \lesssim 0.7$ is adopted to evaluate the characteristic velocity of the viscous fluid.

Figure 5 shows the correlation between the evaluated Ca and ΔP . It is indicated that the evaluated Ca monotonically increases as ΔP in both cases of wettabilities. It is also indicated that the evaluated Ca becomes smaller than that in the better wettability case.

Figure 4. Examples of temporal variation of the averaged impregnation rate under different pressure difference for bare fiber mat.

Figure 5. Correlation between the evaluated capillary number and pressure difference.

The observation results of macrovoids after the fluid impregnation in the field of view are shown below. Figure 6 illustrates an image of the fiber bundles immediately after the flow front of the fluid passes through the field of view with (a) bare fiber bundles (better wettability) and (b) coated fiber bundles (less wettability). The macrovoids are formed and left behind in all the gap between the warp and the weft under $\Delta P = -0.6$ kPa. As the absolute value of ΔP increase, the number of macrovoids formed and left in those regions decreases. Under $\Delta P = -2$ kPa, less number of macrovoids are created in the gaps between the warp and the weft. Even after the formation of the macrovoids, one would see some of them are removed away by the flow of the viscous fluid. Furthermore, under larger pressure difference ($\Delta P = -5$ kPa), no macrovoid formation is observed, and thus no macrovoids remain in the bundles. This is consistent with the tendency shown in previous studies [2,5,8] that the macrovoid fraction decreases as Ca within a region of smaller Ca than the threshold to form microvoids. On the contrary, in the case of (b) less wettability, no macrovoids are formed under any ΔP adopted in this study. The formation of macrovoids is suppressed by lowering the wettability under the capillary number where macrovoids are formed in good wettability cases. The mechanism of such suppression is described below focusing on the flow front behaviors.

Figure 6. (a) bare fiber bundles and (b) coated fiber bundles after the fluid impregnation under (i) $\Delta P = -0.6$ kPa , (ii) $\Delta P = -2$ kPa , (iii) $\Delta P = -5$ kPa.

Figure 7 indicates successive images of the behavior of the flow front in the case of (a) bare fiber bundles (better wettability), and (b) coated fiber bundles (less wettability) under $\Delta P = -0.6$ kPa. The intervals between frames are of 5 seconds for both cases. The top images are the raw image data. In the bottom, the position of the flow front is emphasized for the sake of easy tracking on the raw images. In the case of bare fiber bundles (better wettability case), the flow front of the test liquid preferably advances along/in the warp, and the weft never suppresses the advance of the flow front. Thus the flow front along/in the warp always has a lead against that between the warp. Then, the side of the flow front impregnating adjacent the warps slightly move laterally along the weft to contact the other side of the flow front advancing along the next warp. Then, the coalescence of the sides of the flow front takes place to form a bubble by the necking of the ‘bridged section’ of the test fluid. This is a typical process to form bubbles in the gap between the warp and the weft especially under low ΔP , which is similar to the process shown in the previous studies [1,2,5]. In the case of (b) coated fiber bundles (less wettability), on the contrary, the weft prevents the advancement of the flow front impregnating along the warp for a while (in this case, 15 seconds or more). As the result, the contact, coalescence, and necking processes described above in the case of the bare fiber bundles are not generated. That is, the disturbance of the

flow front advancement along the warp results in no bubble formations. We find that it is possible to prevent the impregnation to the weft by reducing the wettability between fluid and fiber. As a result, one can realize almost uniform impregnation in the direction of the net pressure gradient in the mold.

Figure 7. Temporal variations of impregnation behavior of the fluid focused on the flow front with $\Delta P = -0.6$ kPa. (solid lines: flow front on fiber bundles, dashed lines: flow front under fiber bundles) (i) bare fiber bundles (ii) coated fiber bundles.

Figure 8 indicates successive images of the behavior of the flow front under larger pressure difference ($\Delta P = -2$ kPa) than the case as shown in Fig. 7: rows (a) and (b) indicate the cases of bare fiber bundles (better wettability) and coated fiber bundles (less wettability), respectively. The time intervals between the frames are of 5 seconds for both cases. Top and bottom images are the raw data and the images with the enhanced flow front, respectively, as shown in Fig. 7. The solid curves indicate the detected positions of the flow front located beneath the bundles (or, near the bottom substrate), and the dashed curves indicate those located above (or, far from the bottom substrate). In the case of (a) bare fiber bundles (better wettability), the flow front of the test fluid impregnating along/in the warp does not receive significant resistance by the weft, and the impregnation continues smoothly, as seen under $\Delta P = -0.6$ kPa. However, because of the higher impregnation velocity of the entire fluid compared with the case of $\Delta P = -0.6$ kPa, the precedence of the flow front adjacent the warps to that between the warps is not maintained (see the image, for instance, at $t - t_0$ [s] = 10). Therefore, the contact, coalescence, and necking processes between the flow front are not generated, and thus the macrovoids are hardly formed. In the case of (b) coated fiber bundles (less wettability), on the contrary, the macrovoids are not formed because the flow front along/in the warps stagnates because of the weft for a while, as seen under $\Delta P = -0.6$ kPa. It is found that, even when the macrovoids are not formed, the process is completely different by reducing the wettability between fluid and fiber. In addition, in the region of capillary number where the macrovoids are not formed and/or trapped, by controlling the impregnation to the weft, the precedence of the flow front adjacent the warps to that between the warps is not kept, and thus almost uniform impregnation along the net pressure gradient on average is realized.

Figure 8. Temporal variations of impregnation behavior of the fluid focused on the flow front with $\Delta P = -2$ kPa. (solid lines: flow front on fiber bundles, dashed lines: flow front under fiber bundles) (i) bare fiber bundles (ii) coated fiber bundles.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

We investigate the effect of wettability between the viscous fluid and the fiber on the liquid impregnation process for a single-layer woven glass-fiber mat settled between the flat parallel plates by experimental approaches. A series of experiments are conducted under different designated pressure differences. We prepare two kinds of fiber mats; the bare (uncoated) fiber mat (as the case of better wettability), and the fiber mat coated with a fluorine-based coating agent (as the case of less wettability).

We illustrate different impregnation behaviors of the viscous fluid due to the difference in the wettability. We indicate the correlation between the driving pressure difference ΔP and the corresponding capillary number Ca . We also indicate the effect of the wettability on the formation processes of the macrovoids.

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REFERENCES

- [1] N. Patel and L. James Lee, Modeling of void formation and removal in liquid composite molding. Part II : Model development and implementation, *Polymer composites*, Vol. 17, 1996, pp. 104-114.
- [2] V. Rohatgi, N. Patel, and L. James Lee Experimental investigation of flow-induced microvoids during impregnation of unidirectional stitched fiberglass mat, *Polymer Composites*, Vol. 17, 1996, pp. 161-170.
- [3] J. Slade, K. M. Pillai, and S. G. Advani, Investigation of unsaturated flow in woven, braided and stitched fiber mats during mold-filling in resin transfer molding, *Polymer Composites*, Vol. 22, pp. 491-505.

- [4] R. Matsuzaki, S. Kobayashi, A. Todoroki, and Y. Mizutani, Flow control by progressive forecasting using numerical simulation during vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 45, 2013, pp. 79-87.
- [5] M.K. Kang, W.I. Lee, and H.T. Hahn, Formation of microvoids during resin-transfer molding process, *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 60, 2000, pp. 2427-2434.
- [6] J.S. Leclerc and Edu Ruiz, Porosity reduction using optimized flow velocity in Resin Transfer Molding, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 39, 2008, pp. 1859-1868.
- [7] J.M. Lawrence, P. Frey, A.A. Obaid, S. Yarlagadda, and S.G. Advani, Simulation and validation of resin flow during manufacturing of composite panels containing embedded impermeable inserts with the VARTM process, *Polymer composites*, Vol. 28, 2007, pp. 442-450.
- [8] C.H. Park., A. Lebel, A. Saouab, J. Breard, and W. Lee, Modeling and simulation of voids and saturation in liquid composite molding processes, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 42, 2011, pp. 658-668.
- [9] J. Varna, R. Joffe, L. A. Berglund, and T. S. Lundstrom, Effect of voids on failure mechanisms in RTM Laminates, *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 53, 1995, pp. 241-249.
- [10] C. DeValve and R. Pitchumani, Simulation of void formation in liquid composite molding processes, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 51, 2013, pp. 22-32.